

The Ainu language helps to clarify the initial meaning of the Taoist concept *de* 德

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Abstract

The Taoist concept *de* (or *te*) 德 is quite vague. The concept of *de* that is the main stumbling block in understanding Taoism. According to A. Schuessler, the Taoist concept *de* 德 (Old Chinese **tək*) is in the same word family as the concept of “to get”. Earlier it was shown that the Ainu language is a relative of the Sino-Tibetan family, and that Ainu is a relic of the Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) language. The concept *de* is a cognate with the verb “to get” *de* 得, which in PST had the form **tək*. This form is a cognate with the Proto-Ainu word “hand” **dek*; the corresponding PST form is **lək*. Thus, it is possible to state that the concept *de* (**tək*) initially meant “acquired” “gotten”, “taken” or even “looted”. The gotten item is vital energy/vital force. *De* is accumulated/gotten vital energy.

Key words: Taoism; *de*; *te*; comparative religion; Ainu

1. Introduction to the problem

The key concepts of Taoism are *dao* (or *tao*) 道 and *de* (or *te*) 德.

If the concept of *dao* is more or less clear (it is usually translated as “way”), the concept of *de* is quite vague. It would not be a big mistake to say that it is the concept of *de* that is the main stumbling block in understanding Taoism.

The concept of *de* is usually translated as “virtue”, “grace”, “moral virtue”, which is incorrect. In this paper I want to clarify the initial meaning of the concept of *de*.

2. Schuessler’s and Pulleyblank’s notes on the concept of *de*

According to A. Schuessler, the Taoism concept *de* 德 (Old Chinese **tək*) is probably in the same word family as the concept of “to get” *de* 得 (Old Chinese **tək*), and perhaps is also connected with the concept “straight”, “right” *zhi* 直 (Old Chinese **drək*) 直 “straight; right”. Also, Schuessler quotes the proposal spoken out by E. G. Pulleyblank that *de* 德 and *de* 得 are cognate with the Tibetan word *thub* meaning “a mighty one”, “one having power and authority” (Schuessler 2007)

I suppose that the most realistic interpretation is the idea that the concept of *de* is connected with the verb “to get”.

3. The word *de* is a cognate with Proto-Sino-Tibetan **tək* “to get” and with Proto-Ainu **dek* “hand”

It is amazing and noteworthy that the Ainu language helps to clarify the initial meaning of the concept of *de*.

Earlier it was shown that the Ainu language is a relative of the Sino-Tibetan family. Ainu and Sino-Tibetan languages demonstrate notorious structural (Akulov 2016, Nonno 2025b, Nonno 2025c) and lexical similarities (Akulov, Nonno 2026, 2025a, 2025c, 2025b, 2024; Nonno 2025a). Ainu is not a distant relative, but is a member of the Sino-Tibetan family, and Ainu is a relic of the Proto-Sino-Tibetan language (Akulov, Nonno 2026: 3 – 4).

In the Ainu language are preserved very archaic forms which sometimes are older than the corresponding Proto-Sino-Tibetan forms. And also, in Ainu culture are preserved very archaic concepts which can help to clarify the initial meaning of some concepts of Chinese culture. (A culture is generally congruent structure with language: any culture can be represented as an ordered pair <A; W> where A is a set of concepts and W is a set of distributions of concepts, and any language can be represented as ordered pair <A; W. where A is a set of morphemes/concepts and W is a set of distributions defined over A. In other words, culture is actually the concept level of a language.)

The Taoism concept *de* is a cognate with the verb “to get” *de* 得 which in Old Chinese had the form **tək*, and in Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) had the form **tək*¹. The PST word **tək* “to get” look much alike the Proto-Ainu word (PA) “hand” **dɛk*², and also PST and Proto-Tibeto-Burman (PTB) forms for “hand” **lǎk*³ and **dak*⁴ evidently are connected with the PA word “hand” **dɛk*.

Thus, it is possible to state that the concept *de* (**tək*) initially meant “accumulated”, “acquired” “received”, “gotten”, “taken” or even “looted”. The received/gotten is vital energy/vital force. *De* is accumulated/gotten vital energy.

4. *De* and *ramat*

The concept of *de* corresponds to the Ainu concept of *ramat*.

The word *ramat* consists of two components: *ram* meaning “thorax”⁵ and the component *at* that is close to such verb as *an/oka* “to exist”⁶. The word *ramat* can be translated as “vital force exists”, “soul exists”.

Although words *ramat* and *de* are not related, they come from different roots, but the Ainu word *ramat* definitely expresses exactly the same meaning as the Taoist word *de*.

5. Conclusion

It is correct to understand the concept *de* not as karma (which is categorically wrong), and not as a virtue, but as vital energy, vital force. This is how the Chinese understood *de* when they thought about their history. For example, the fall of dynasties was explained by the lack of *de* of emperors, the appearance of Buddhism in China was explained as the return of *de* of the ancient Chinese emperors to China.

¹ Starostin 2005b.

² Akulov, Nonno 2026

³ Starostin 2005a.

⁴ Wkitionary 2026.

⁵ Akulov, Nonno 2026b: 16

⁶ Akulov 2006: 200.

And also, the fact that the Ainu language is the key for understanding the main concepts of Taoism means that the ancients of which spoke Kong zi and Lao zi were actually the ancient Ainu people.

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